

Role of movement data in creating inclusive school settings for students

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Abstract

There is limited robust evidence to support public decision-making around inclusive school settings. Education has been compared negatively with the medical profession in terms of its engagement with evidence-based practices. However, innovative techniques, such as sensor data are able to support decision-making around accommodating vulnerable groups at school. This paper measures complex social phenomena through modern sensing technologies while students are in their break at school with a special focus on Dutch primary schools. Analyzing and interpreting movement data sheds light on how to evaluate school settings during leisure time, and propose possible improvements to the school leisure policy, and its environmental characteristics.

Introduction

In academic research and policymaking, there has been a strong emphasis on measuring and evaluating the inclusive setting based on the academic performance of students. This overlooks the fact that an individual student may be actively included in the classroom, while being simultaneously excluded from the informal community, for example during breaks. These experiences are not captured with attendance and academic performance indicators and require insights into the child's behavior while participating in informal environments. School breaks are often unstructured time for leisure, play and interaction with peers in a setting where adults supervise at a distance (Baines, E., & Blatchford, P., 2019). However, there is limited robust evidence to support public decision-making around inclusive school settings with group dynamics during school breaks. This study thus proposes a data-driven policymaking approach to studying and evaluating non-classroom settings of students at school as a complementary measure to academic performance when looking at the inclusiveness of schools. This is done by using wearables as a modern sensing technology and data analysis tools to collect, process and understand the data collected from movements on the schoolyard.

Research/policy question

How can analysis of student's activities during breaks inform policy decisions concerning inclusiveness at school?

Research methodology and Data used:

A total of 76 children aged between 5 and 13 years old participated from 12 different classes of a primary special education school in the central area of the Netherlands. Participants are students at school. All parents were asked to provide written consent for their children to participate in this research and only pupils with informed consent from their parents participated. Children were asked to wear a belt with adjustable length on their waist if they are willing to participate in this research. Each belt was supplied with three sensors Global Positioning System (GPS) logger, Proximity tags (Radio Frequency Identification based Devices - RFID) and Multi-Motion Receiver (MMR) to measure the physical environment, social environment and activity of the child, based on Küller's (1991) human-interaction model:

- a. *Physical environment:* GPS loggers are adopted to assess the location of children in the schoolyard.
- b. *Social environment:* Proximity tags are used to unravel the closeness centrality of individual children in their social network.
- c. *Activity:* MRR measures the physical activity level of children

Key findings:

We explored the use of movement data on three levels:

1- Physical environment

By mapping the GPS data into spatial bins, we obtained a heatmap of the schoolyard. Heat maps provide information about space utilization in general levels which enables us to understand how physical features (e.g., fences, parking lots etc.) and play structures (e.g., swings, soccer field etc.) could impact children's behavior, moves, and use of space. In Figure 1, the heatmap of a particular playgroup is depicted in which the intensity is higher in areas where play structures (i.e., football field, multi-function structure, and sandpit) are located. This map demonstrates how children utilize the space, and how that is impacted by the play structures.

Figure 1- The heatmap of location for a particular playgroup: the higher duration of visit, the warmer color and the higher number of children, the larger black circle is. The most heated areas are around football field, multi-structure and sandpit.

2- Social environment

Using the proximity tags, we created a social network of children in the schoolyard. The closeness centrality measure (Freeman, L. C. 1978) of children is calculated afterward to analyze the social density in the schoolyard. This measure scores each child based on their 'closeness' to all other children in this social network. It, therefore, measures how much individual children are attached to their social network. Figure 2 shows the social network graph of children in which nodes/children are colored based on their closeness score (following the color bar) and are positioned based on dyad interactions with peers.

Figure 2- Social network graph: nodes are positioned based on the duration of interactions with peers: The higher the duration of the dyadic interactions between two nodes/children, the closer the distance between the two nodes. Edge's thickness is based on the duration of interactions between pairs of nodes. Nodes are colored based on closeness centrality score, sized based on the number of interacted partners and labeled based on their diagnosis:

- ASD = Autism Spectrum Disorder,*
- PD = Physical Disability,*
- ADHD = Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder,*
- DLD = Developmental Language Disorder,*

3- Activity

By categorizing children's physical activity levels into sedentary, light, moderate, and vigorous, we analyzed children's activity levels in different playgroups. This information enables us to understand how the schoolyard layout and environmental features could impact children's activity and how that may differ in children with different special needs, ages, and gender. As shown in Figure 3, the youngest playgroup (c), has a relatively lower activity level by having the highest portion of Sedentary activity compared to others.

Figure 3- Physical activity level of three playgroups obtained by the accelerometer data: (a) grades (8-12), (b) grades (5-8) and (c) grades (1-4)

Conclusions:

This study discusses the results of ongoing work within an interdisciplinary research project with the collaboration of computer scientists, psychologists, architects, and public policy analysts. We deploy the human interactions model (Küller, R., 1991) to analyze the environmental factors that affect a child's emotional status over time. Following this model, the sensor data is analyzed within three main interconnected elements: 1) social environment, 2) physical environment and 3) activity. Based on current results, there is great potential in using the children's movement data to understand social interactions and gain insights into how students experience leisure time at school. Analyzing and interpreting the movement data sheds light on how to evaluate the school settings during leisure time, and proposes possible improvements to the school leisure policy, and its environmental characteristics. The tools introduced in this paper can therefore support policymakers in evaluating the school design in terms of inclusivity.

References

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